

The Securities Exchange Board of India Investor Grievance Redressal System

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Abstract

Investors may be individuals and institutions. Individual’s investors operate alongside institutional investors in the investment arena. However, their characteristics are different. Individual investors are large number but their investable resources are comparatively smaller. They generally lack the skill to carry out extensive evaluation and analysis before investing. Moreover, they do not have the time and resources to engage in such an analysis.

Institutional investors, on the other hand, are the organization with surplus funds who engage in investment activities. Mutual funds, investment companies, banking and non-banking companies, insurance corporations, etc. are the organizations with large amounts of surplus funds to be invested in various profitable avenues. These institutional investors are fewer in number compared to individual investors, but their investable resources are much larger. The institutional investor engages professional fund managers to carry out extensive analysis and evaluation of different investment opportunities. As a result their investment activity tends to be more rational and scientific. They have a better chance of maximizing returns and minimizing risk.

- *Investors are the backbone of the securities market.*
- *They determine the level of activity in the securities market and the level of activity in the economy.*
- *Many investors may not possess adequate expertise/knowledge to take informed investment decisions.*
- *May not be aware of the complete risk-return profile of the different investment options. may not be fully aware of the precautions they should take while dealing with market intermediaries and dealing in different securities.*
- *They may not be familiar with the market mechanism and the practices as well as their rights and obligations.*

Keywords: Investors, Grievance Redressal, Investment, Cumulative, SCORES, SMAC, ATR.

Introduction

Investor protection is one of the most important elements of a thriving securities market or other financial investment institution. Investor protection focuses on making sure that investors are fully informed about their purchases, transactions, affairs of the company that they have invested in and the like. SEBI had issued guidelines for the protection of the investors through the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Disclosure and Investor Protection) Guidelines, 2000.

Objective of SEBI

The SEBI has been entrusted with both the regulatory and developmental functions. The objectives of SEBI are as follows:

- Investor protection, so that there is a steady flow of savings into the Capital Market.
- Ensuring the fair practices by the issuers of securities, namely, companies so that they can raise resources at least cost.
- Promotion of efficient services by brokers, merchant bankers and other intermediaries so that they become competitive and professional.

So we can understand that primary function of SEBI is the protection of the investors' interest and the healthy development of Indian financial markets. No doubt, it is very difficult and herculean task for the regulators to prevent the scams in the markets considering the great difficulty in regulating and monitoring each and every segment of the financial markets.

SEBI Guideline

- **Issue of guidelines:** SEBI has issued guidelines to companies. This guideline are for bringing transparency in their operations and also for avoiding exploitation of investors by one way or the other. SEBI keeps watch on all intermediaries and see that they follow the guidelines in the right spirit. It also takes panel actions when the guidelines are not followed. These steps give protection to investors.
- **Public interest advertisements:** SEBI issues public interest advertisements to enlighten investors on the basic features of various instruments and minimum precautions they should take before choosing an investment.
- **Dealing with complaints of investors:** The investors can make complaints to SEBI if they face problems relating to their investment in industrial securities and financial assets. SEBI receives thousands of complaints relating to non-receipt of refund orders, allotment letters, non-receipt of dividend or interest and delays in the transfer of shares and debentures.
- **Investor education:** SEBI is aware that investor education and educate investors through publishing of newsletters. These publications are for the education, guidance and protection of investors.
- **Disclosures by companies:** SEBI has introduced norms for disclosure of half yearly unaudited results of companies. It has also revised the format of prospectus to provide more information to investors. SEBI conduct inspection, inquiries and audits of stock exchanges, intermediaries and self regulating organizations and takes suitable remedial measures wherever necessary. Further, it penalizes those who undertake fraudulent and unfair trade practices.
 - a. Specify the manner in which the matters relating to issue of capital, transfer of securities and other matters shall be disclosed by the companies.
 - b. No company can make an issue of securities unless a draft prospectus has been filed with SEBI.
 - c. The offer document, through which the securities are issued, is to be prepared strictly as per the requirements of SEBI Guidelines.
 - d. No company shall make an issue of securities unless it has made an application for listing of securities at a stock exchange.
 - e. No company can make public issue unless all existing shares must be fully paid.
 - f. Companies raising capital through public issues of securities are required to deposit 1 per cent of the issue amount with the designated stock exchange. This deposit is released by

the stock exchange only. SEBI issues NOCs to companies after satisfactory redressal of complaints against them as received by SEBI. During 2016-17, NOCs were issued to 80 applicant companies. NOCs to 43 companies were not issued as the applications were incomplete or due to unsatisfactory redressal of investor grievances.

Steps taken by SEBI

- a. Security Market Awareness Campaign (SMAC) was started with a motto “An educated investor is a protected investor.”
- b. Invest with Knowledge” was the message spread by this campaign.
- c. Workshops Advertisements Educative material All India Radio – Information provided through AIR Programs frequently.
- d. SEBI launched toll free helpline service numbers 1800 22 7575/ 1800 266 7575 on December 30, 2011. The helpline service is available every day from 9:00 am to 6:00 pm (except on declared public holidays in Maharashtra) to investors from all over India. The help line service is available in English, Hindi and various regional languages. During 2016- 17.

Grievance Redressal system

SEBI has been taking various measures to expedite the redressal of investor grievances. The grievances lodged by investors are taken up with the respective listed company or intermediary and monitored on a regular basis. Grievances pertaining to stock brokers and depository participants are taken up with concerned stock exchanges and depositories for redressal and monitored by the concerned department through periodic reports obtained from them. Grievances pertaining to other intermediaries are taken up with them directly for redressal and monitored regularly by SEBI’s concerned department. The company/intermediary is required to respond in a prescribed format in the form of an action taken report (ATR). Upon the receipt of an ATR, the status of grievances is updated. If the response of the company/intermediary is insufficient / inadequate, follow-up action is initiated. SEBI takes appropriate enforcement actions (adjudication, 11B directions, prosecution, etc.) as provided under the law where progress in redressal of investor grievances is not satisfactory.

The SEBI Complaints Redressal System (SCORES) has helped investors in obtaining real time information on the status of their grievances. Investors can log on to SCORES at any time and from anywhere and check the status of the grievance with the help of a user-name and password provided at the time of lodging a grievance. Alternatively, investors can also call the SEBI toll free helpline to check the status of their grievances. Since SCORES has made it possible to receive grievances online this helps SEBI take up issues very fast, including those that may require a policy change. Further, since companies are required to file an ATR within 30 days of receipt of a complaint, in case of any failure SEBI can initiate action against the company depending on the merit of the case. The salient features of this system are:

- Centralized database of all complaints;
- Online movement of complaints to the concerned entities;
- Online upload of Action Taken Reports (ATRs) by the concerned entities; and
- Online tracking of status of complaints by investor

SEBI’s Complaints Redress System

The number of investor complaints received by SEBI on a cumulative basis increased from 29,63,454 as on March 31, 2016 to 30,03,454 as on March 31, 2017. But, during the same period the number of pending actionable complaints reduced from 5,452 to 4,476 (Table #1).

Table 1 Cumulative pending grievances on SCORES

Financial Year	Grievances Received		Grievances Redressed		Pending Actionable Grievances*
	Year -wise	Commulative	Year -wise	Commulative	
1	2	3	4	5	6
2008-09	57,580	26,74,560	75,989	25,03,560	49,113
2009-10	32,670	27,06,895	42,742	25,46,302	37,880
2010-11	56,670	27,63,565	66,552	26,12,854	28,653
2011-12	46,548	28,10,113	53,841	26,66,695	23,725
2012-13	42,411	28,52,524	54,852	27,21,547	11,410
2013-14	33,550	28,86,074	35,299	27,56,846	9,147
2014-15	38,442	29,24,516	35,090	27,91,936	5,736
2015-16	38,938	29,63,454	35,145	28,27,081	5,452
2016-17	40,000	30,03,454	49,301	28,76,382	4,476

Note: *excludes complaints against which regulatory action has been initiated.

SCORES was launched in June 2011. Details of complaints in the table from 2011-2012 onwards are as per SCORES.

Figure 1 Cumulative pending grievances on SCORES

Figure 1 indicates that the number of pending grievances has been steadily declining over the years due to expeditious disposal by SEBI. Moreover, out of the 4,476 pending grievances as on March 31, 2017, 3,492 grievances have been pending for less than six months. Further, only 984 grievances were pending for more than six months as on March 31, 2017 as compared to 1,973 grievances pending for more than six months as on March 31, 2016.

SCORES enables investors to lodge complaints directly online and such complaints are considered ‘e-complaints.’ During the year, 22,304 e-complaints were received compared to 22,969 received during the previous financial year. While investors can lodge e-complaints on SCORES, any physical complaint received against any of the entities in the SCORES database is also uploaded on SCORES and thereby converted into an e-complaint and action similar to that with regard to an e-complaint is taken.

The SCORES system has been working satisfactorily and has helped in making the complaint handling and redress mechanism more efficient. A review module was implemented in SCORES

in July 2016 wherein an investor can make a one-time request for review of a complaint closed by a SEBI dealing officer within 15 days of the closure of a complaint. As on March 31, 2017, SEBI had received 2,347 complaints for review out of which 695 have since been closed.

Scores Survey

The Researcher was conducted a survey on SCORES at Rayalaseema Region of Andhra Pradesh, investor satisfaction with the system. The survey was conducted with 750 investors who were selected randomly within the Rayalaseema Region of Andhra Pradesh i.e Kurnool, Kadapa, Anantapur and Chittoor. The questionnaire were designed in such a way the investors how best he/she receiving results from the SEBI and accountability towards the all grievance problems etc. The salient features of this system are:

For the analysis purpose and to know the Redressal mechanism and what kind of Complaints investors have been experienced analyzed thru the structured questionnaire in Rayalseema region [89]. The result of grievance redrssl system is differing from district to district in Rayalseema region.

Table 2
Investors Grievance Redressal System

Sl. No.	Complaints	District				Total (%)
		Kurnool	Anantapur	Kadapa	Chittoor	
1	Non-Receipts Dividend/ Interest/Rights/Bonus/AMFI Role/Mutual Fund Role	10	21	12	18	61(11)
2	DEMAT Charges are too heavy	30	31	34	32	127(23)
3	DEMAT Charges on unlisted or non-traded shares to be removed	5	8	4	12	29(5.2)
4	Brokerage Commission are too high/ transparency	50	43	32	21	146(26)
5	Shares do not appear in Demat Account so enough/web based Grievance proposal	51	33	47	26	157(28)
6	Shares sale proceeds do not come to you in time/Investors website response etc	4	4	6	16	30(5.4)
	Grand Total	150	140	135	125	550(100)
	X²	46.75190595				
	P - Value	0.00004 Significant				

Source: Field Survey

Data Type: Normal Data

Test applied: χ^2 test

Level of Significance: 95%

Degree of Freedom: 15

Results: Significant

From table 2 that in Rayalseema region from total sample i.e.550 investors response is that 26% of the investors are saying that the commission and other charges are too high from company to company in India and 23% of investor were responded regarding annual charges of the DEMAT Account is differ from Broking Company to Company. 11% respondents are regarding non receipt of dividend and AMFI transparency has to improve and 28% of the investors are not satisfying regarding web based grievance proposal. 5.4% of the investors are unable to get sale proceeds. Charts from 3.3.27(a) to 3.3.27(f)

The test results, there is significant difference among the Investors Grievance Redrssl System in Rayalaseema Region since $p < 0.001$. SEBI needs to strengthen Grievance Redrssl System in order to restore the investor's confidence in stock market in India.

Figure 2 (1)
Investors Grievance Redressal System

Figure 2(2)

Figure 2(3)

Figure 2(4)

Figure 2(5)

Figure 2(6)

Recommendations/Conclusions

- Investors should make the investment with proper planning keeping in mind their investment objectives.
- Investors should also consults the brokers or agents to seek information and advice but their decision should not merely be based on agents advice rather the decision should be based on their careful investigation.
- Some of the investors also suggested that there should be more training and awareness camps by SEBI to guide the investors how to invest in stock market and what are the
- Various formalities that must comply with. This will encourage investment and discourage speculation.
- There should be local tribunals that deals with the problems of investors in different districts of state, because we see very few people approach SEBI or company law board and they go

to exchange cells as per their convenience, so the people living away from exchanges, prefer to not filing complaint.

- There should be flexible working hours of stock Exchanges, so that the Govt. Employees, Private employees and students can approach them as per their convenience.
- More than 90% of investors were satisfied the present system of SCORES in Rayalaseema Region of Andhra Pradesh
- During 2016-17, SEBI conducted a survey on SCORES through an independent agency to gauge investor satisfaction with the system. The survey was conducted with 10,000 investors who were selected randomly across the four cities of Mumbai, New Delhi, Ahmedabad and Kolkata. These cities were chosen based on the maximum number of complaints received. The survey broadly indicated that more than 75 per cent of the respondents who had filed complaints with SEBI expressed satisfaction with the grievance redressal mechanism.

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